

1.1 Evaluation methodology

Several research methods in the field of human–computer interaction (HCI) have been established to evaluate software. Depending on the stage of software development, evaluations are classified as summative or formative approaches. Summative assessment entails appraising a fully prepared tool for a specific application, whereas formative evaluation occurs during the software development process and paves the way for tool enhancement. This distinction is crucial because the evaluation procedures and strategies used by assessors are highly influenced by the goals underlying an evaluation.

To meet the above-mentioned evaluation objectives, we conducted focus group discussions. A focus group discussion is an effective qualitative strategy for capturing individual opinions. This was necessary in this work because the discussion of the FAIR-Decide tool was a complex matter that was also context dependent. The focus group research approach was selected, as it offers a framework for in-depth conversations and an environment in which to acquire original ideas and strategies for working on a research topic in a collaborative manner.

Participants

The participants were chosen using purposive and snowballing sampling techniques. We held focus group discussions with 17 participants (Table 1) for both scenarios of the evaluation; non-industry and industry; (discussed below), from November 2021 to January 2022. Six participants from FAIRplus performed a non-industry evaluation while 11 pharmaceutical professionals undertaking the industry evaluation were invited by email to provide new insights into the FAIR-Decide tool.

To improve the validity of the research, most of the participants (14 out of 17) had not taken part in the previous stages of the research (interviews and workshop). Participants were organised and assigned to seven focus groups. Their previous FAIR-related experiences were considered to adequately qualify them to evaluate the developments in both scenarios. The participants are therefore fairly representative of potential users of this tool.

Table 1: Summary of focus group participants

Evaluation type	Project/Company	Participant	Date
Non-industry evaluation (The FAIRplus project)	1. e-Tox ¹	P1, P2, P3	25th Nov 2021
	2. IMIDIA ²	P4, P5	2nd Dec 2021
	3. EBISC ³	P6	10 th Dec 2021
Industry evaluation (Pharmaceutical companies)	1. AstraZeneca ⁴	P7, P8, P9, P10	25th Nov 2021
	2. Johnson & Johnson ⁵	P11, P12, P13, P14	8th Dec 2021
	3. Novartis ⁶	P15, P16	14th Dec 2021
	4. GSK ⁷	P17	17th Jan 2022

Procedure

The evaluation proceeded through the two following scenarios:

1. Non-industry evolution scenario (The FAIRplus team): A critical requirement was to obtain feedback early on in the development process, and this could be achieved in a straightforward manner by enlisting assistance from a group of researchers who are members of the FAIRplus project. A non-industry decision-making scenario was selected for the first evaluation. This scenario was focused on non-industry case studies shared by the FAIRplus project, which are IMI datasets and not pharmaceutical sources. This assessment has a benchmark on a dataset that was FAIRified by the team that did it to measure against as these datasets were selected and FAIRified. The comments and early feedback from the participants who work on FAIR implementations were important in shaping and improving the FAIR-Decide tool.

1 <http://www.etoxproject.eu>

2 <https://www.imi.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets/imidia>

3 <https://ebisc.org>

4 <https://www.astrazeneca.com>

5 <https://www.jnj.com>

6 <https://www.novartis.com>

7 <https://www.gsk.com>

2. Industry evaluation scenario (pharmaceutical companies): The second evaluation involved simulating the tool’s use in the industry of interest. This scenario was focused on industry case studies shared by pharmaceutical professionals, which are pharmaceutical datasets. A pharmaceutical industry evaluation was essential in assessing whether the FAIR-Decide tool satisfies the goals for which it is designed and addresses the requirements of the pharmaceutical industry.

- **Focus group design**

For both scenarios, we conducted virtual focus group discussions, as this was a safe and accessible data collection avenue during the Covid-19 pandemic. The PhD candidates met with the participants online (via Zoom) and facilitated/moderated the discussions through answering the participants’ questions and providing clarification if needed. All the sessions, each lasting for approximately an hour, were audio-recorded, transcribed and anonymised. We created the materials required to effectively perform the evaluation study. These materials included a focus group agenda, which was attached to the invitation email sent to the participants. The focus group discussion was carried out in three main phases: testing, discussion and assessment (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Workflow for the focus group discussions

1- Testing phase

This phase started with an ice-breaking activity related to the aim of the focus group discussions, the participants' demographic information and the introduction to the FAIR-Decide tool and its purpose. The PhD candidate then shared a link to the tool (https://www.qualtrics.manchester.ac.uk/jfe/form/SV_b1vL8dqgyrmfAz4) with the participants and instructed them thus:

If you are being asked to make a decision on FAIRifying an existing dataset, and you have the FAIR-Decide tool aimed at helping you assess the potential outcome of the FAIRification process on the basis of principles underlying cost–benefit analysis.

2- Discussion phase

In this phase, we discussed with the participants their thoughts and experiences in using the FAIR-Decide tool. To engage them, we used the Miro platform, which offers a space for collaborative discussions. We then referred to the question guide in directing the conversation as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The focus group discussion guide

No.	Area of discussion	Proposed question(s)
1	Participants' expectations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Does the FAIR-Decide tool help you in making a decision on FAIRification? If so, how?
		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• What is your most significant observation about the tool?
2	Participants' experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Please describe your experience with using the FAIR-Decide tool.

No.	Area of discussion	Proposed question(s)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are your thoughts on this tool?
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the most helpful section of the output to you? Why?
3	Strengths and weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are some of the strengths of the tool, and where does it fall short?
4	Comments and recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What can be improved?
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you have additional suggestions and recommendations?

3- Assessment phase

In this phase, we asked the participants to assess the effectiveness and suitability of the FAIR-Decide tool. The participants also expressed their final thoughts about the tool.

Focus group analysis

The transcripts of discussions were examined through thematic analysis. This analytical approach was selected because it pinpoints discussion content that is worth scrutinising and uncovers the meaning of such content and its particular implications for research. More precisely, this method entails creating small chunks of data and then assigning a code to each chunk. Drawing from the evaluation study objectives, we created a framework that encompasses four categories: (1) the potential value of the tool, (2) the strengths and weaknesses of the tool, (4) common and specific points and (4) recommendations.

Ethics

Ethical considerations were vital in conducting this research, and adhered to the regulations of the Faculty Ethics Committee of the University of Manchester. Specifically, the researcher used the university's ethics decision tool, which stated formal ethical approval was not required, due to participants acting in a professional capacity; that is, there was no need for a formal ethical review of the evaluation activity. To adhere to the university's guidelines, the following procedures were followed: The respondents were given the Participant Information Sheet (PIS) and asked to complete the consent form prior to the study.

Pre-evaluation stage (pilot testing)

Once the FAIR-Decide tool was developed, it was then presented to two experienced evaluators for initial testing. The design of the tool was iterated over twice with feedback from the aforementioned individuals, thereby revealing additional indications of the usefulness of the methodology on a practical level. The following subsections present the perspectives derived from the pilot testing:

Usability testing perspective

During the development phase and prior to the evaluation, we shared the tool with an independent researcher (evaluator) who had extensive practical knowledge of user experience (UX). We asked for usability testing and the identification of areas that can improve UX. The evaluator tested the tool and provided documented feedback, met with the PhD candidate and discussed improvement for refining of the tool over a month, which amounted to more than four sessions of deliberations approximately weekly. The comments revolved around the clarification of some of the questions in the tool, the simplicity of its grammar and the provision of additional information, if needed, to enhance UX. The evaluator was also added to the original software as a collaborator to improve UX with the developed tool. She tested the tool several times, and each time, she provided feedback on improving and simplifying the tool from a UX perspective. Figure 2 presents an example of email messages received from this evaluator.

I had a go and played around with the tool. It looks very good! Well done! I really liked the format of the output. Just a few user-experience comments:

For dependency questions good to have checks, e.g. metadata (if I say no metadata exist then in the next question, I should be not asked about community standards but to be presented as a question only if I stated earlier that metadata exist)

For human resources -->

Justify your selection in this section.

Did not understand this, you mean in the last question or the whole section?

I would make it more specific in each 'justify your selection in this section' question for every time this is used for extra clarity about what you are referring to.

I wasn't able to download a pdf, but just view the report.

I can go to producing the report without having answered any questions. Maybe you should check if all questions are answered so you do not get half questions answered which can result in wrong assessments. à so a check that all (important) questions are answered before clicking the next button in each page. It might be that you do not care about some questions, but you definitely want others to be answered.

In the results page, if I do not click the arrow button and I close the window and then click the link again I am presented with the same output. Maybe refresh this each time the link is clicked? This would be good as you do not want other people to see the report produced by others, addressing any privacy concerns.

Hope it helps! If you need anything else, let me know!

Kind regards,

Figure **Error! No text of specified style in document.2**: Sample email messages received from the UX tester

As shown in Figure 2, the evaluator tested the tool in a semi-final phase and asked for enhancements in terms of the dependency questions and the output of a report. In this phase, we had not finalised how the questions may relate to one another. In terms of the output from the tool, the evaluator suggested visualisation in the form of a gauge chart.

FAIR implementation perspective

During the development stage of the FAIR-Decide tool and prior to the evaluation, we also shared the tool with an evaluator who had expertise in FAIR implementation and worked in pharmaceutical companies for several years. The evaluator tested the tool as a laboratory-based researcher who worked for a pharmaceutical company a few years ago. In that use case, he conducted an experiment wherein he incorporated different types of entries on the

chemistry of tissues and antibodies into a spreadsheet that used internal identifiers. He realised that he had carried out a similar experiment in a recent study, which might be helpful. More precisely, he needed to link that data to new datasets for which some other external identities were used. Therefore, the basic idea would be that somebody would go through the data individually, perform searches on the Internet (or similar tasks), endeavour to determine what they are and link the spreadsheet to appropriate identifiers.

The evaluator tested the tool and spent at least 20 minutes completing the assessment. The comments focused on expanding some of the questions in the tool and adding more information to certain questions related to identifiers and ontologies, as some users might be unfamiliar with some of the FAIR concepts presented in the tool. He also suggested paraphrasing some of the questions to ensure ease of understanding and prevent misinterpretation. For example, he recommended replacing the accessibility model with licensing or the authentication and authorisation process, which are more common in the pharmaceutical industry. In terms of the output from the tool, the evaluator advised sending an email to a user containing their output and offering a functionality that prints or saves a report as a PDF file. In addition, he suggested providing an overview that compares costs and benefits in a single graph/matrix for easy comparison and comprehensibility. Figure 3 provides a screenshot of the email received from the FAIR implementation tester, and Figure 4 illustrates his selection for the tool.

Initial testing

Tool feedback
 3.15pm start; 3.36pm end
 select dataset - the 'other box' did not disappear - should be skipped if you answered this Q
 - i would change 'i' icon to say 'reveal question', since 'i' normally means information
 - for the text boxes i would add 'please add more information', eg. 'requires further investigation'
 - 'cost saving descriptoin' is unclear
 - access model descriptoin a bit unclear as my 'use case' is an internal spreadsheet in pharma
 - How likely will anonymisation affect data accuracy?
 - needs to be rephrased
 - What is the importance or weight of this factor in your FAIRification decision?
 - not clear if it means quality/mamagement. help info is not useful
 - How likely is this data to use ontologies?
 - its retrospective, so the question is will the FAIRified data require ontologies?
 - How long would it take to FAIRify this data?
 - what if i have no idea? In my use case I have no idea at all
 - Do you need to recruit more staff to perform FAIRification?
 - again no idea
 - Are your internal IT applications compatible with one another?
 - ditto

I didn't really understand the output. I saw a page which scored all the different answers I have, but no summary telling me what I learnt from this...

Figure 3: Sample email messages received from the FAIR tester

Cost-benefit Assessment Report

Date: 30 Nov 2021
Time: 3:48 AM

Part 1: FAIRification Decision Structure

A- General information to structure the FAIRification decision.

Your Role	Roles of other Stakeholders	The Project Name	The Data Type
Researcher	Data steward, Researcher, Laboratory head	Spreadsheet to FAIRify from 2 years ago	Compound and screening

B- The goals of FAIRification and its scope.

FAIRification Goal	FAIRification Scope
Convert local names IDs to URI	Convert all chemical names, and protein/ antibody names

Figure 4: Example of a selection made by the FAIR evaluator

With the pilot evaluation from the two perspectives as grounding, we worked on these constructive comments and tried to improve the pilot version of the FAIR-Decide tool prior to the evaluation proper. Here are some of the improvements made: The tool is now able to handle dependency questions; it has the functionality to send an email to users that includes a results report, and it allows users to print reports or save them as PDF documents, allowing those results to be shared, compared and reviewed. The output of the tool is also presented in a more visual manner (i.e. via a weighted decision matrix).

Evaluation (two scenarios)

This section contains details regarding the evaluation of the FAIR-Decide tool. The evaluation was based on two scenarios as follow:

- **Evaluation 1: Non-industry scenario (The FAIRplus project)**

The non-industry evaluation was aimed at the type of testing routinely conducted by members of the FAIRplus project, who are familiar with the selection of datasets for FAIRification and have experience of making FAIRification decisions across several IMI projects. Three retrospective project datasets (case studies) that were FAIRified by FAIRplus were chosen. Accordingly, focus group discussions were conducted with three groups, each consisting of two to five participants.

- **The first project: e-Tox**

The e-Tox project is a completed IMI project that is a publicly available subset of the total toxicological information manually compiled from the contents of pre-clinical studies as experimental results. This project was one of the first projects undertaken by FAIRplus and was challenging as no formal process had yet been defined, and the dataset itself posed challenges (e.g. determine alternative identifiers, and selection of relevant ontologies). We conducted the corresponding focus group discussion with three participants, who were all familiar with the case study and performed FAIRification for e-Tox (Table 3).

Table 3: Participant information: e-Tox evaluation

ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P1	Data manager	Data and knowledge management in R&D	10–15	Enhance the findability of e-Tox data (subset) by describing and standardising the project data to be able to integrate with other similar datasets / projects
P2	Laboratory head	Data curation	5–10	
P3	Data scientist	Data management, standards for clinical and omics data	5–10	

The decision scenario was for the participants to decide whether to FAIRify the e-Tox dataset. The session commenced with the PhD candidate sending the link to the tool (web-based form) to the participants through the chat functionality of Zoom, specifying the aim of the tool and introducing its modules. The participants started testing the tool by independently completing three modules: (1) the structure of decision making on FAIRification, (2) the benefit module and (3) the cost module.

After this, they shared their results (i.e. in the form of the cost–benefit assessment report), compared and contrasted their results, and discussed their thoughts and opinions. Each participant received an email (containing a response summary and attachment of the assessment report) upon completion of the modules and presented the results of their assessment for discussion of the similarities and differences with the group.

- **The second project: IMIDIA**

IMIDIA is also a completed IMI project that concerns therapies for slowing down the progression of diabetes, with a focus on pancreatic beta cells. The project encompasses omics (human and non-human), pre-clinical and clinical (vital signs, genetics, diagnosis, etc.) data. It was selected for evaluation in this work, as it was one of the recent FAIRification projects

carried out within FAIRplus and was accompanied with several legal issues related to the FAIRification process (e.g., it comprises sensitive data, and access extends only to metadata). The FAIR-Decide tool has an extensive segment devoted to the legal aspects and costs associated with FAIRification (how legal issues would be resolved, whether anonymisation is needed, and so on). We invited four people who participated in this FAIRification project, but only two responded and attended the focus group sessions, as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Participant information: IMIDIA evaluation

ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P4	Data steward	Ontology annotation and development, metadata modelling and data integration	10–15	Increase interoperability of IMIDIA by standardising annotations using ontologies to make the data more public.
P5	Researcher	Biochemistry and ontologies	5–10	

As with the e-Tox evaluation, the participants were asked to test the tool independently, but one of them seemed less familiar with the project, repeatedly asking the other about relevant details. Both participants performed the assessment independently and, upon completion, received email messages directing them to discuss the results of their evaluation, compare and contrast, and express their thoughts regarding the tool.

- **The third project: EBiSC 1**

EBiSC 1 is a completed IMI project that is a unified, non-profit iPSC⁸ (Induced Pluripotent Stem Cells) bank that provides scalable, cost-effective, and consistent instruments for novel medicine development to researchers in academia and industry. This project was selected for

⁸ <https://stemcell.ucla.edu/induced-pluripotent-stem-cells>

evaluation in this study because it required extensive FAIRification efforts by FAIRplus team members. We sent an invitation to four prospects who performed FAIRification for this project, but only one agreed to take part in this study (Table 5).

Table5: Participant information: EBiSC1 evaluation

ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P6	Data manager	Data and knowledge management in R&D	10–15	Improve the findability of cell line information on web catalogue

In this session, we followed the same procedure as that done in the previous sessions, but because there was only one respondent, the exchange was structured as an individual interview rather than a focus group discussion. Correspondingly, this session was shorter than the others. Fortunately, the participant was actively engaged and shared his experiences in a detailed manner.

- **Evaluation 2: Industry scenario (pharmaceutical companies)**

Evaluation 2 was aimed at gaining deeper insights and more practical ideas from professionals who work in several pharmaceutical companies. This was a critical step, as the FAIR-Decide tool was based on data that were collected mainly from the interviews and the collaborative workshop. We selected five pharmaceutical companies affiliated with the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA) to derive broad perspectives, but only four responded to the invitation email and agreed to take part in this evaluation.

The first company: AstraZeneca

We invited four prospective participants with different roles in the R&D department of AstraZeneca to evaluate the FAIR-Decide tool. These individuals were pharmaceutical professionals (Table 6) responsible for implementing FAIR principles and deciding on

implementations of the FAIRification process. The corresponding focus group discussions converted to four sessions (interviews), with each participant having his/her own use case and testing the tool based on that case.

Table 6: Participant information: AstraZeneca

ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P7	R&D strategy lead	Knowledge management and legal process	15–20	Align the dataset to standard control vocabularies and standard identifiers
P8	Product manager	Drug discovery and marketing	10–15	Integrate critical elements of lab results
P9	IT professional	R&D data management	10–15	Ensure that all screening results can be linked unambiguously to the original tested sample
P10	Data director	Data integration, linked data in pharmacogenomics	15–20	Have data interoperable so that it can be combined with other datasets

The second company: Johnson & Johnson

We also invited four Johnson & Johnson-based prospects who assumed different roles in the company’s R&D department. They were pharmaceutical professionals (Table 7) tasked with implementing FAIR principles and making decisions on FAIRification. The focus group discussions were conducted simultaneously, but each of the participants evaluated the tool independently based on his/her own use case, after which all of them discussed the assessment of the tool and shared their thoughts and opinions.

Table 7: Participant information: Johnson & Johnson

Participant ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P11	Head of computational chemistry	Computational chemistry and drug design	15–20	Link subjects, samples, RNA data and clinical outcomes for better understanding of disease biology
P12	Project manager	Data management plans and project sustainability	5–10	Avoid duplication of Clinical Trial data to enable faster access and integration
P13	IT director - data platforms	Data standards and modelling	10–15	Increase potential re-usability of the image data for other projects
P14	Manager - data platforms	Data management	5–10	Build a virtual metadata tracking system linked to decentralised biobanks

The third company: Novartis

We invited four Novartis employees who also worked in different capacities in the company's R&D division, but only two responded and agreed to take part in this study. As with other participants, these were pharmaceutical professionals (Table 8) who are familiar with the FAIR principles and make decisions regarding FAIRification. The focus group discussions converted to two sessions (interviews), with each participant preferring to test the tool on the basis of his/her own use case.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.: Participant information: Novartis

ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P15	Technical associate director	Data ontology and mapping domain	10–15	Align on a cell annotation workflow
P16	Head of data strategy	Ontologies, curation, data strategy	5–10	Improve findability of image data

The fourth company: GSK

We also invited four R&D employees from GSK to evaluate the FAIR-Decide tool, but only one agreed to take part in this study. The participant was a pharmaceutical professional (Table 9) responsible for implementing FAIR principles and deciding on the FAIRification process.

Table 9: Participant information: GSK

ID	Role	Background	Years of experience	Use case
P17	Data manager and IT specialist	Information architecture, data modelling and ontology	10–15	Increase interoperability and enhanced metadata for 'omics data pertaining to drug usage on human subjects

Evaluation results

This section summarises the feedback received from the participants during two rounds of evaluation (non-industry and industry scenarios). It begins with an overview and then proceeds to detail the evaluations made on the basis of four categories identified from the data analysis: (1) the potential value of the tool, (2) its strengths and weaknesses, (3) common and specific points and (4) suggestions for enhancement.

- **Evaluation 1: Non-industry scenario**

As previously stated, the non-industry evaluation was intended to conduct testing that involved individuals who are familiar with the FAIRification process in the FAIRplus project. This assessment has a benchmark on a dataset that was FAIRified by the team that did it. This means that the already FAIRified dataset can be used as a baseline for comparison (e.g., They did this - does the tool give them the answer they wanted in hindsight?). This is the key part of this scenario as that there is a baseline to measure against as these datasets were FAIRified. Note that the individuals who took part have less focus on business issues related to FAIRification decisions.

Overview of the findings

The findings indicated that, as anticipated, the tool supports decision making on FAIRification that is based on cost–benefit assessment. Some ideas were also collected that will improve the guidance given for completing evaluations using the tool. The participants collectively acknowledged the value of the tool and its intended purpose, especially for users who are less familiar with FAIR implementations. The discussion revealed that the tool can adequately fulfil the function it was designed for. Nevertheless, the respondents identified room for improvement.

Focus group outcomes

In what follows, a detailed analysis of the four categories of the focus group data is presented.

1. The potential value of the tool

The participants were satisfied with the way the FAIR-Decide tool effectively handles FAIRification decisions on the basis of cost–benefit aspects. They were impressed by the level of progress achieved with the tool in addressing this difficult and critical issue.

“It is amazing. It is not an easy task, and I think you are already at a very good level.”

(P2)

The effectiveness of the tool in structuring decision making on FAIRification was unanimously noted. Participants were pleased with the fact that the tool helps determine whether FAIRification is a worthwhile undertaking on the grounds of evaluated costs and benefits.

“I think it is good. It helps answer whether FAIRification will be worth what you are planning to do.” (P1)

The participants also acknowledged the efficacy of the tool in arriving at a decision consistent with those made by FAIRplus experts. More precisely, the tool generates a decision matrix reflecting the value of FAIRification on the grounds of assessments of cost and benefit factors. This consistency was observed in IMIDIA and EBISC 1, with FAIRification assessed as worthwhile, given the low costs and considerable benefits derived from it (Figure 10). In EBISC 1 FAIRification was deemed worthwhile by experts. As stated by a participant (EBISC 1):

“It came up with the same decision that we came to in the squads. So, we decided it was helpful to do that, and the tool came up with the same answer. So that’s good.” (P6)

Figure 10: Sample assessments of EBiSC 1

2- Strengths and weaknesses

The three group discussions highlighted that the FAIR-Decide tool effectively facilitates group decision making by a geographically distributed team. The participants also indicated that the independent assessments encourage objectivity in evaluation and eliminate unhealthy behaviours in group decision making such as influenced by apparent seniority and supposed knowledge or hidden intentions in business organisations.

“It is good. The three of us did that independently, and we received an email. We have three independent assessments. So, we can compare all the different roles to see if there is a pattern.” (P2)

As another strength, the visualisation of output (the assessment report) was noted by the participants as useful in understanding results related to scores and informing their decisions. Most of the participants were highly engaged, in particular, with the pointer for cost and benefit factors.

“I like the visualisation thing; the pointer is really nicely visualised.” (P4)

Some of the respondents also described the guidance on completing assessments (the information button located next to most of the questions in the tool) as helpful in carrying out evaluations.

“The “tips” button helped; the examples helped with answering the questions.” (P6)

In terms of weaknesses, some of the participants were less satisfied with a few of the questions in the tool, describing these as subjective. This was the case with the queries related to individual expectations regarding cost savings from FAIRification (e.g. ‘Do you expect FAIRification to save on costs in the re-creation of data at a later time?’).

“Overall, I like the way that things go, but sometimes, the questions should be more objective or less subjective with respect to larger FAIRification projects, depending on individual users.” (P3)

A few of the participants criticised the one-time completion of the tool. They expressed a preference for filling in items over time and reserving part of the assessment for a later period. Their rationale was that someone less familiar with a dataset or FAIR concepts would be able to seek information and complete an assessment later on (e.g. after a week). They preferred to store a result and redo the same assessment, updating relevant sections, and see the effect on the scores over time.

“You really need to finish it in one go if you need to check on stuff in a dataset or FAIRification aspects. I may do this while I wait for people to get back to me on issues that I don’t know. That’s a very good scenario.” (P4)

3- Common and specific points

As this is a non-industry evaluation made by individuals who have less focus on business issues, most of the participants commonly judged business aspects (e.g. competitive advantage and the importance of FAIRification for an enterprise) as irrelevant. They experienced difficulty in comparing the importance and novelty of a dataset (section 1 in the cost module), which involves rating the importance of the dataset and determining whether

FAIRifying it can generate a competitive advantage for a business. Most of them reviewed the guidance (accessed via the information button) more than once.

“I think there’s some questions about the kind of costs that are very role dependent and have a business focus. This is particular for a business or drug companies.” (P4)

Some of the participants agreed that the FAIR-Decide tool allows for flexibility in completing an assessment. That is, answering all sections is optional, enabling the skipping of a few questions that are inapplicable to a given role.

“With regard to flexibility for the user, if I were a biologist or a clinician, for example, I might know a lot about data but less about other aspects. So, it would be good if you can just look at the issues that you know and ignore the others.” (P4)

In terms of specific points, a few of the participants called attention to the provision of support for collaborative decision making through an aggregation of independent assessments and a comprehensive summary of a group decision.

“I would like to have a tool that can do kind of an aggregation, like a summary. Like saying, okay, we have so many answers for this question, and here is the overall result.” (P2)

A few of the participants also found the weighted score for each factor slightly confusing. Their explanation was that such a weighting question should be raised once, which means that one weight should be applicable to all related factors. Incorporating this feature, however, is not possible in this kind of weighted assessment because each factor has its own weight.

“The weight question – assigning a weight for each factor was a bit confusing.” (P1)

4- Recommendations

The suggestions and comments concentrated primarily on improving the layout of the user interface, adjusting the wording of some of the questions and providing additional information in an assessment report. These are summarised as follows:

- The layout of the web-based tool can be improved by using different tools that are more professional.

“I think that I would recommend using a different tool, but obviously you don’t have time to do that. And then you could improve the layout that suffers as a consequence.” (P6)

- The wording of some of the questions and the instructions for completion should be enhanced.

“It is kind of hard to extrapolate the meaning of some questions. I guess the questions are quite straightforward, but some of them need to be read a couple of times.” (P3)

- Providing more information in an assessment report (the assessment output) would be helpful and provide supporting evidence.

“It would be good if the report was a bit clearer, what the take-home message is and what supporting evidence is included.” (P4)

- Considering the monetary value of costs and benefits (e.g. how much it costs to implement FAIRification) can support business decision making.

“I wish there was a way to just sort of evaluate the quantitative data of the FAIRification by trying to frame it in terms of how much could be gained.” (P1)

- Carrying out an assessment collaboratively rather than independently can be effective and less time-consuming. Note that this conflicts with the advantages of doing it separately.

“It’s still very valuable to me to do that as a team. We know why we reached this point and this result.” (P2)

Some of these suggestions and comments were immediately addressed by the PhD candidate. For example, the wording of the guidance (accessed via the information button, located next to some of the questions) was adjusted. Other recommendations were left for future work.

- **Evaluation 2: Pharmaceutical industry scenario**

The pharmaceutical industry evaluation was aimed at testing with pharmaceutical professionals to gain deeper insights from the intended users of the FAIR-Decide tool. This assessment involved pharmaceutical professionals making FAIRification decisions on pharmaceutical datasets (as industry case studies).

Overview of the findings

The findings indicated positive responses from the evaluators and included comments and suggestions for improving this tool in a way that renders it applicable to a wider range of FAIRification decision-making situations in their companies. The evaluators were generally satisfied with the performance of the tool, although they provided constructive suggestions for particular decision-making situations and future enhancements. The overall evaluation indicated that the FAIR-Decide tool is an appropriate and effective decision support aid for FAIRification in pharmaceutical R&D, especially for junior employees who are less familiar with the associated costs and expected benefits of FAIRification.

Focus group outcomes

This section presents a detailed analysis of the four categories of data derived from the industry-specific focus group evaluation.

1- The potential value of the tool

The participants were pleased that the FAIR-Decide tool could facilitate decision making on FAIRification on the grounds of cost and benefit aspects. They regarded the tool as a promising step towards the implementation of FAIR principles in their companies, as it provides an easy way to adopt the tool in real-world settings.

“I think it looks very promising as a tool. This is an important contribution. I think it will take for us to have tools that make it easier for people to adopt them.” (P10)

Most of the participants appraised the tool as valuable, considering it a starting point for paying attention to the cost of applying FAIR principles to legacy datasets.

“I think that’s valuable. We start thinking about anything relative to the cost of doing retrospective tasks.” (P17)

The respondents also acknowledged that the decision-making structure accompanying the tool guides pharmaceutical professionals in understanding whether performing a very costly process is worth it and whether its benefits can be balanced.

“I think just the process of thinking about FAIRification with this tool to guide you is quite useful, which I think more people need to do, at least in my organisation.” (P17)

In a similar vein, some of the participants described the tool as an educational source that can support decisions on FAIRification. It involves several steps in informing final decisions.

“I can certainly see the educational value. It’s the decision-making step, which I appreciate as being much harder.” (P10)

The participants added that the potential value of the tool can be leveraged to convince senior staff to make decisions on FAIRification.

“We usually present FAIRification decisions to senior team members or executives. So, it helps to be able to try to convince somebody else. I guess that makes this a useful tool.” (P15)

2- Strengths and weaknesses

The participants praised the visualisation of decisions as one of the most important strengths of the FAIR-Decide tool. They highlighted the decision matrix, which they deemed suitable for team discussions (Figure 10).

“The decision matrix is good. I think the matrix fits a lot of what we talk about in our team.” (P15)

Figure 10: Sample assessments of the weighted decision matrix

A number of the participants averred that the visualisation (the gauge chart for costs and benefits) is more helpful for managers in pharmaceutical organisations.

“If I am a manager trying to justify the cost of FAIRification, it would be helpful for me to see this at a glance. So, I actually think that this is a pretty good visualisation.” (P10)

Another strength acknowledged by most of the participants is the effectiveness of the tool in handling or raising legal issues, which is one of the challenges confronting the conversion of datasets into FAIR materials, especially in pharmaceutical organisations.

“I think there is value in flagging all the legal and ethical aspects, obviously, around that data.” (P7)

Furthermore, the participants appreciated the efficient simplicity of the FAIR-Decide tool, and they were pleased with the cost and benefit factors captured by it. They asked whether the tool is available in open source form so that they can share it with their colleagues.

“I think I really like the tool in terms of the fact that it’s very pragmatic. It’s a simple thing. I wonder whether it is open source.” (P8)

They likewise recognised the flexibility of the tool, in which the assessment of most cost and benefit factors is optional. Certain factors may not always be applicable to all types of datasets and assessor roles.

“The fact that you can skip questions is good; this flexibility, I think, is a good point.” (P16)

A weakness raised by a few participants is the lack of specificity regarding the minimal knowledge required to do an assessment (prior to actual evaluation).

“One must have minimum knowledge prior to answering the questions.” (P8)

In addition, the participants underscored the need for background material as a guide for users as they initiate assessment.

“You might want a little bit more background material, a sort of user guide on preparing an assessment.” (P10)

A few of the respondents lamented the difficulty arising from the fact that assessment is restricted to only one dataset at a time. They recommended incorporating the option to assess multiple datasets at the same time (e.g. those constituting a project).

“It is a little hard to decide on this, as it can evaluate just one dataset. I want to use it in a bigger project or drug discovery campaign.” (P15)

A handful of them criticised the tool as missing quantitative features (both costs and benefits in monetary terms).

“For someone who requires more quantifiable aspects, operating in a more business decision-oriented space means quantifiable issues are going to be key parameters.” (P16)

3- Common and specific points

The participants regarded the tool as a suitable source of education about making a decision on FAIRification. They viewed it as illuminating cost–benefit aspects in a structural manner, thereby adding to their knowledge of several facets related to FAIRification.

“You can use it as an educational tool for junior members, which is a very valid point.”
(P17)

Another collective reaction from the respondents was their emphasis on the need for the tool to have an analysis structuring template that is customisable to each organisational purpose.

“This is a template for a structured analysis that can and probably should be modified by individual organisations because they can specify the first issue that they want to make sure of. A template may not capture all the factors that are very important in deciding on FAIRification.” (P11)

In terms of specific points, a few of the participants asserted that the tool should enable the assessment of the costs and benefits of a project (multiple datasets) rather than one dataset across an organisation.

“This is very focused on a single dataset, but I’m not interested in individual datasets. I’m more interested in being able to do it across things, and the priority is really driven by the business owner.” (P7)

A number of the respondents expressed preference for application to a specific type of datasets (e.g. clinical data), viewing each datatype as corresponding to a different situation.

“Structuring the tool depending on the type of data you want to create would be a worthwhile exercise for me.” (P8)

4- Recommendations

Below is a summary of the comments made by the evaluators on ways to enhance the FAIR-Decide tool. These suggestions centre on improvements to the layout of the user interface,

adjustments to the wording of some of the questions and supplements to the information in an assessment report.

- Extend the tool to handle multiple datasets.

“It is a little hard to decide on this, as it can evaluate just one dataset. I want to use it in a bigger project or drug discovery campaign.” (P15)

- Improve the layout of the tool to transform it into an interactive version.

“I appreciate how complex the task you are attempting to do here, but I think you are going to need to work through a lot more interactions to understand the decision-making process.” (P7)

- Convert the tool into open access technology to reinforce the chances that pharmaceutical professionals will find it.

“Are you going to keep this website up, and is it something that I can share with colleagues? Because I’m thinking in particular about people in our data office who are charged with FAIRification.” (P10)

- Connect this work with relevant communities (e.g. Pistoia Alliance) for collaboration with industry.

“I was looking at the Pistoia Alliance guidelines and was curious about how your work can be connected to existing tools and knowledge that are out there isolated in the community.” (P11)

- Supplementing explanations in the results section is crucial.

“This looks great to me. I would still have to explain it to somebody else. I would like to understand how to use that tool fully.” (P15)

- The tool should have a function for handling collaborative decisions.

“I guess I found it an interesting tool, but I am not sure how I would really use it in my work. It’s a collaborative decision.” (P15)

Most of the suggestions are related to tool interaction, indicating that this remains a considerable area for improvements to the user interface. The comment on rewording the questions showed that the participants desire more transparent communication using the tool, as well as less ambiguous terms and a functionality for facilitating clarity. The recommendation on augmenting result explanations was targeted at the evaluation scenario rather than the tool itself. Some of the participants (particularly the IT professionals) called attention to the essentiality of incorporating specifically metadata aspects into an evaluation.

Note that we immediately addressed some of the comments (e.g. rewording for clarity of meaning). The rest of the recommendations (e.g. conversion into an open source tool) were left for future work.

- **Evaluation discussion**

Results

Overall, the evaluation results were positive. The participants in both the evaluation scenarios found the FAIR-Decide tool promising. The discussions across focus groups confirmed its suitability for a wide range of decision-making situations, albeit certain improvements are needed to address particular complex situations. The tool’s performance showed that it can fulfil requisite functions effectively. Suggestions and comments were shared on various aspects of the tool and could form the basis for further work.

The findings of the generic and specific evaluations reflected that the objectives, reproduced below (Table 11), were achieved.

Table 1: Summary of the key findings of the evaluation

No.	Key findings
1.	All the key objectives or subjective reasoning aspects of decision making in the non-industry scenario were covered by the tool.

2.	All known errors were identified during and after the two evaluations. Where appropriate these have been corrected, which were appropriate.
3.	The focus group discussions reflected that the tool is applicable to practical decision making on FAIRification, as evidenced by the output of the assessment (The cost–benefit assessment report was consistent with two out of the three cases/decisions in the non-industry evaluation).
4.	The discussions across the seven focus groups demonstrated the suitability of the FAIR-Decide tool for its intended environment. This was confirmed by agreement in the discussion, especially for the pharmaceutical industry scenario.
5.	The discussions also verified that the adopted approach (the weighted sum of cost–benefit factors) is ideally suited to tool development, but a few of the participants did not like the weighting and described it as a confusing scheme.

Comparison of the evaluation scenarios

There was some variability in the judgement of the evaluators in the two assessment rounds, possibly because different people have varying perspectives on the same issues—an inevitable phenomenon. On balance, however, the evaluators of the industry-specific scenario were more actively engaged than those of the non-industry situation. This reflects the fact that the industry scenario is more realistic and that the FAIR-Decide tool (which was designed on the basis of the requirements raised in the collaborative workshop) satisfies pharmaceutical user requirements. This finding may also be attributed to the following:

- The participants in the industry evaluation understood business aspects, as most of them have a business focus compared with the assessors of the non-industry scenario, who have a technical focus.
- The participants in the non-industry evaluation seemed to have more knowledge about FAIR implementation (e.g., the goal of the FAIRification and the scope) than those in the industry evaluation as each participant did the evaluation for his/her own use case with less focus on the FAIRification goals, whereas in the non-industry evaluation all participants did the same use case with prior information about the aim and the scope of the FAIRification (as these datasets were selected and FAIRified).

As a consequence, the feedback from the industry evaluation was more substantial in terms of quality and depth. The suggestions and comments from the non-industry group centred on

the layout of the tool and the addition of technical features, whereas those from the industry group covered nearly every aspect of the tool. This is probably because of the factors below:

- The non-industry evaluation was not specific to pharmaceutical R&D dataset (which is what the tool was designed for) but focused on selected IMI datasets.
- There were not as many complex situations and sensitive data involved in the non-industry scenario (actual pharmaceutical datasets, with the participants focusing only on IMI datasets).

In general, both evaluations were considered successful, as manifested by how well the FAIR-Decide tool performed under the decision-making scenarios and the positive response of the evaluators. The assessors were of the view that future improvements would further facilitate decision making on FAIRification under more complex situations.

The chosen methodology (focus group discussion) advanced the testing of all aspects specified in the evaluation objectives. Important aspects of the entire evaluation process include the following:

- Testing the tool by enlisting the help of individuals with different roles and from different organisations was effective.
- The focus group discussions, including the testing, discussion and assessment phases, covered most of the major factors that needed to be tested and were useful in eliciting profound perspectives, thus enabling the derivation of essential feedback from the evaluators.
- All the evaluators of the industry-specific scenario had considerable experience in the field (FAIRification implementation), ensuring a relatively accurate assessment of the tool.
- Both groups of evaluators were familiar with the implementation of FAIR principles. Finding people who are familiar with such a task in the pharmaceutical industry was vital to this evaluation. The evaluation approach was appropriate in this regard, although it was recognised that during the focus group discussion, a few of the participants were less aware of the practical implementation of FAIR principles (technical aspects such as identifiers, and ontologies).

The evaluation approach was limited in the following respects:

- The non-industry evaluation should have been conducted earlier, as this would have guaranteed a more formative process.
- A full demonstration for all the evaluators before the assessment commenced would have been helpful. This was not possible given time constraints.

Generally, it was hoped that the FAIR-Decide tool would be tried/deployed on a real-world project (pharmaceutical project). Unfortunately, there was no access to actual pharmaceutical datasets. This task can be included in the further evaluation and refinement of the tool.